

Supplementary Information for article:

“From countries to cities: assessing climate ambition with a multi-level fair-share allocation framework”

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Figure S1 | Cities reporting the use of fair share methods in the design of their emissions targets, from 2020 to 2023. Data based on the responses of cities to the 2020 to 2023 CDP Questionnaires where cities reported that they considered their target followed the fair share methodologies recommended by the Science Based Target Network: i) Deadline 2020; ii) Science-Based Targets Initiative (SBTi); iii) Tyndall Method; iv) One Planet City Challenge (OPCC) highlighted in Red or from initiatives such as v) Race to Zero that also claim the use of fair share allocations highlighted in orange. For the fair share methodologies recommended by the Science Based Target Network, search terms include: “Deadline 2020”, “Science-Based Targets”, “Yes, our jurisdiction considers the target to be science-based”, “Tyndall”, “One Planet City Challenge”, “OPCC”, and “SBTi”. For the Race to Zero category, search terms include: “Race to Zero” and “RtZ”.

Supplementary Methods

Global level

Figure S1 | Global scenario (IMP-LD - MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM 1.0 - LowEnergyDemand_1.3_IPCC) decomposition between its positive, negative emissions and emissions from LULUCF. LULUCF emissions will be excluded from the fair share allocation, while positive and negative emissions will be allocated separately, before being aggregated.

Regional level

Figure S2 | Regional emissions timeseries as aggregations of national responsibility allocations.

Figure S3 | Regional emissions timeseries as the aggregation of national capability allocations.

Table S1: Summary of data availability by types of entities.

Entity Type	# with emissions allocations	# with emissions target
Region (below national level)	3318	160
City	234	68

Table S2: Summary of warming alignment of various entities' emissions targets.

Entity type	Alignment	Count	Percent of entities aligned
Country	1.5 °C	90	50.6%
	2.0 °C	8	4.5%
	> 2.0 °C	80	44.9%
Region	1.5 °C	8	5.0%
	2.0 °C	9	5.6%
	> 2.0 °C	143	89.4%
City	1.5 °C	15	22.1%
	2.0 °C	11	16.2%
	> 2.0 °C	42	61.8%

Table S3: Comparison of ambition, based on warming alignments, between subnational governments and their respective national governments.

Entity	Ambition compared to national level	Count	Percent of entities
City	As Ambitious	44	64.7%
City	More Ambitious	24	35.3%
Region	As Ambitious	144	90.0%
Region	More Ambitious	2	1.3%
Region	Less Ambitious	14	8.7%

Figure S4 | Geography of emissions allocations in 2030 for countries (a) and regions (b), and of ambition assessments of the 2030 emissions targets of national (c) and local governments (d). Here, the historical responsibility is accounted since 1990 (as opposed to 1970 in the main manuscript).